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Improving innovation and multidisciplinary competences among bachelor of engineering students

H. Løje¹

Senior Innovation Officer
Technical University of Denmark
Ballerup, Denmark
E-mail: halo@dtu.dk

P. Andersson

Senior Executive Educational Development Officer
Technical University of Denmark
Lyngby, Denmark
E-mail: pea@llab.dtu.dk

S. Grex

Associate Professor
Technical University of Denmark
Ballerup, Denmark
E-mail: sarg@dtu.dk

ABSTRACT

From society and industry, there are increasing requirements for skilled and well-educated engineers who can develop new solutions through innovation and this have pushed universities to meet these requirements by having an increasing focus on developing innovation and entrepreneurship programmes within Engineering Education. Furthermore, there is also a demand for the graduates to be able to work multidisciplinary and to be able to use generic skills in their work. In this paper, the research question is how to enhance innovation and multidisciplinary competences of engineering students? This is a central question in order to educate engineers that can create sustainable solutions for the environment, for products and to secure future workplaces. In this paper, a new mandatory course for Bachelor of Engineering students at the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) "Innovation Pilot", will be described and how the challenge to improve innovative competences and the ability to work in multidisciplinary teams with engineers from other disciplines are solved. Results from a survey regarding the students' innovation competences and interdisciplinarity show that we have succeed in creation of understanding of what innovation is. However interdisciplinarity is still difficult for the students to handle.

¹ Corresponding Author
H. Løje
halo@dtu.dk

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INTRODUCTION

From society and industry, there are increasing requirements for skilled and well-educated engineers who can develop new solutions through innovation and this have pushed universities to meet these requirements by having an increasing focus on developing innovation and entrepreneurship programmes within Engineering Education [11]. Furthermore, there is also a demand for the graduates to be able to work multidisciplinary and to be able to use generic skills in their work [2].

The aim of this paper is to address the research question “How to enhance innovation and multidisciplinary competences of engineering students?” This is a central question in order to educate engineers that can create sustain solutions for the environment, for products and for securing future workplaces. In this paper, a new mandatory course for Bachelor of Engineering students at the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) called Innovation Pilot, will be described and how the challenge to improve innovative competences and the ability to work in multidisciplinary teams with engineers students from other disciplines is solved.

1 BACKGROUND FOR FOSTER INNOVATION IN EDUCATION

Innovation can be defined in many ways and in general, innovation can be seen as the process of translating an idea into a products or service which creates value for someone or something. Business is an important factor as innovation includes an economical aspect and can be seen as the result when new ideas are matured and marketed by a company in order to satisfy the needs and expectations of the customers [9].

A number of conceptualized definitions and theoretical approaches have led to several attempts to understand innovation competency. However, the definition varied considerable with different perspectives and approaches [11]. Innovation competences involve a wide range of human abilities and processes such as personal ability (in finding real-life problems and formulating research questions), interpersonal ability (by being open and responsive to diverse perspectives and intentionally constructing collaborative relationships) and implementing ability (by effectively implementing their ideas in useful projects) [11].

Interdisciplinary competences are necessary to manage innovation activity as well as there is a need for the engineers to have knowledge and understanding of other professions involved in the creative and innovation process [7]. Nowadays it is a critical job requirement to be able to work on flexible and always-changing teams and furthermore also to have the capability to recognize an interconnection among a broad range of activities.

Working with innovation requires enhancing of the students skills in creativity but also to give the students higher confidence to deal with uncertainty, ambiguity, and risk-taking [4].

Active learning education aims at providing the students with the opportunity to think critically and through a series of activities that help them to prepare for challenging professional situations which may involve evaluation, problem solving and critical reasoning skills. Problem-based learning is a well-known approach by using a problem solving approach as well as motivating and engaging the student in the learning process [5].

1.1 CDIO as a teaching paradigm

In 2011, the CDIO (Conceive-Design-Implement-Operate) syllabus was updated to version 2.0 [1]. Particularly attention was given to innovation, invention, internationalization and sustainability.

In the Bachelor of Engineering educations at The Technical University of Denmark (DTU), the CDIO-approach to Engineering Education is implemented as the overall teaching paradigm [2].

In September 2014 the first version of the new developed CDIO-based diploma (B.Eng) programs were launched at DTU. The most significant new activity in the education was the introduction of a common 10 ECTS compulsory course in innovation in the later part of the programs named Innovation Pilot. The idea behind this course is to give students the opportunity to collaborate on inter-disciplinary real-life projects. This course strengthens not only innovation skills but personal and interpersonal skills as well [8].

2 THE COURSE INNOVATION PILOT

The outline for the course Innovation Pilot is that the students work in multidisciplinary teams with specific real-life challenges offered by the involved companies.

The companies provide open-ended projects which take a starting point in actual challenges observed by the company. The company is the problem owner and the students should involve the context reality of the company in solving the challenges. The students are responsible for finding ways to apply their unique skills and knowledge to create value in the projects.

The Innovation Pilot course is offered three times a year, twice in the semester periods of 13 weeks and once as an intensive summer course of 6 weeks. At DTU there are 17 study programmes involved and it is expected that approximately 450 students from these 17 study programmes will attend the course during each spring and winter semester. At the beginning of the course, the students are divided into smaller units of up to 60 students running in parallel. Teams are formed so they consist of 4-6 students within a minimum of two disciplines present. The teams are assembled with different competences to be used for the handling the challenge provided by a company.

There are no traditional lectures in the course so the students are expected to have prepared themselves before coming to the class by e-learning. The e-learning material consists of short videos, documents and papers all available at the course site. E-learning gives flexibility and removes the traditional lecture. This is to optimize the time the students have to work together (one full day a week) and to allocate time

for facilitation. All the way through the course, the students work on creating prototypes in the university's workshops facilities.

The course Innovation Pilot is fitting nicely within the framework in CDIO. The course is given for the students during the last semesters of their education and combined their independent use of the disciplinary knowledge they gained with going through all the phases in the CDIO process; Conceive-Design-Implement-Operate. The last phases Implement and Operate in CDIO can be hard to address in an educational setting. In Innovation Pilot the students work also in those phases through the outline for the course where the students work in multidisciplinary engineering teams with a specific open-ended challenges offered by industry companies. The students involve the reality of the company when solving the challenges. Students are introduced to real life problem by direct involvement of enterprises which are engaged from the beginning of the course to propose challenges for the students.

The students attending the course come from 17 different study programmes and they have different experiences working in multiple disciplinary teams and with innovation. Depending on the case some students can easily adapt their educational background with the case work while others find it more difficult. From the course responsible there is focus on that the company challenges should be relevant for engineers and have a technical aspect. Furthermore, there is a focus how student with different educational backgrounds can use each other expertise and also use of generic skills in working with the company challenge.

The teaching in innovation pilot is based on the active learning method “problem based learning” with use of blended learning/flip the class room and workshops and team work. Furthermore, peer-feedback and pitches are used as part of the teaching.

2.1 Course design and learning processes

At the course innovation pilot, the Double Diamond model is used to support the innovation process. Double Diamond is a process model created by Design Council, a British organization, in 2005 [3] and it presents four main stages across two adjacent diamonds. The first diamond in the Double Diamond model concerns exploration of the problem and understanding of the problem. The second diamond is the problem solving phase. Each of the four stages is characterised by either convergent or divergent thinking. The four stages are:

- Discover –identify, exploration research and understand the initial problem.
- Define – limit and define a clear problem to be solved.
- Develop – focus on and develop a solution.
- Deliver – test and evaluate, ready the concept for presentation for the company

Fig. 1. Made by inspiration from the double diamond process model (Design Council, 2005 [3])

During the course, the students run the innovation process twice in two so-called loops, both involving company challenges. In both loops, the students conduct an innovation process structured according to the double diamond model (*Fig. 1*). The first loop takes four weeks and it is a training loop where the students get to know how to work with the double diamond process model with additional methods and tools. In the second loop, 2-3 teams of students work with the same challenge provided by a company and the process is structured as in the first loop, but it is now more up to students to plan their work. The second loop takes 8 week with 3 weeks dedicated to exploring and defining the problem (the first diamond in Double Diamond) and 5 weeks dedicated to problem-solving and prototyping (the second diamond in Double Diamond) [6].

3 APPROACH AND FINDINGS

Since spring 2016, the course innovation pilot has been running three times, and the number of students and company involved has increased over time. In spring 2016, the course ran for the first time and it was an elective course with 42 students. The second time the course was up scaled and had become a mandatory course with 233 students enrolled and at the third time, 272 students were enrolled. The companies involved in the course are mainly small-medium sized enterprises and typical engineering companies [6].

When the course was running in autumn 2016, a questionnaire was made to evaluate the students perception of innovation and interdisciplinary. The questionnaire consisted of questions with regards to innovation and interdisciplinary competences. For each question, there was a scale ranged from “disagree” to “agree” with the possibility to mark “do not know” for each question. In the interests of high response rate, the data was collected anonymously using the program “SurveyMonkey” [10].

A link to the questionnaire was sent to the students at the beginning of the course and again after accomplishment of the course. After collection of the questionnaire data, the results were analysed.

3.1 Findings/results

In autumn 2016, 233 students were enrolled for the course and they were all invited to participate in the questionnaire. At the beginning of the course in autumn 2016, 184(79%) students filled out the questionnaire and after accomplishment of the last course 144(62%) students filled out the questionnaire. However only 182 and 175 students answered the questions regarding innovation and multidisciplinary, respectively in the first round and 137 and 132 students answered the questions regarding innovation and multidisciplinary, respectively in the second round.

There were three questions regarding innovation which the student had to answer and the questions were; “I know what innovation is”, “Innovation is important for an engineer” and “I like to work with open problems”. *Fig. 2* show the results from the three questions from the first questionnaire at the beginning of the course and from the second questionnaire after accomplishment of the course - which can be compared.

Fig. 2. Innovation: ‘I know what innovation is’ (Dark), ‘Innovation is important for an engineer’ (medium grey) and ‘I like to work with open problems’ (light grey). ₁ represents the results from the questionnaire at the beginning of the course and ₂ represent the results from the questionnaire after accomplishment of the course. Y axis is % of total number of answers.

With regards to innovation, more students agree that they know what innovation is and that innovation is important for an engineer after they have accomplished the course. However, there is tendency that there are more from agree to partly agree with regards to the question “I like to work with open problems”.

There were also three questions regarding multidisciplinary which the student had to answer. The questions were “I like to work with persons from my own education”, “I like to work with persons from other educations” and “I believe that multidisciplinary work is difficult”. Fig. 3 show the results from the three questions from the first questionnaire at the beginning of the course and from the second questionnaire after accomplishment of the course - which can be compared.

Fig.3. Multidisciplinary competences: “I like to work with persons from my own education” (dark), “I like to work with persons from other educations” (Medium grey), “I believe that interdisciplinary is difficult” (light) _1 represent the results from the questionnaire at the beginning of the course and _2 represent the results from the questionnaire after accomplishment of the course Y axis is % of total number of answers.

The results show that the students are becoming much more aware of what innovation is when they have finished the course. With regards to multidisciplinary, the picture is not so clear but a large part of the students believe it is difficult to work in multidisciplinary engineering teams after they have done it in innovation pilot. Our experience points to the observation (but no systematic investigation has yet been done in this area), that multidisciplinary is something the students in their study programs only have little experience with. The students ability to grasp the heterogeneity of the problems and their multidisciplinary facets, appear limited for the most parts. However, our expression is that many students really like to work with students from other programs and that they find it fun and motivating.

4 SUMMARY

Interdisciplinary innovation is important for the future engineers. In this paper, we have discussed how the Innovation Pilot-course defines a framework for collaboration between students from different engineering disciplines with aim of enhancing the innovation and multidisciplinary competences. The results from a questionnaire show that we have succeed in creating an understanding of what innovation is. However interdisciplinary is still difficult for the students to handle. In

the future methods to learn and support student's interdisciplinary work need to be developed.

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